

Moon-moon Scattering and the Origin of Irregular and Runaway Moons

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Abstract

Observations of the Solar system show that planetary satellites exist in various configurations; some have circular, co-planar orbits, and these are termed regular satellites. Other irregular satellites, have typically eccentric, inclined, and even retrograde orbits. Regular satellites are formed through core-accretion; similar to planet formation scenarios, but the origin of irregular satellites is still debated. Various formation scenarios have been suggested, involving capture of external unbound objects, either following a disruption of a binary minor planet, interaction of a single planetesimal with the planetary atmosphere of the planet, or through chaotic capture of planetesimals during rapid growth of the planetary embryos. However, it is difficult to reconcile the number of irregular moons with these hypotheses. Here we present a different hypothesis for the origin of irregular moons, through the in-situ formation of regular moons, which then scatter each other into irregular inclined and eccentric configurations. Such interaction could possibly lead to ejection from the system, producing “runaway moons”. We find instability regions where moons similar to the two biggest moons of Jupiter, Saturn and Uranus, could have become dynamically unstable due to mutual interactions. We show that moon-moon scattering in these regions could lead to ejection of moons from the system, and explore the eccentricity and inclination excitations of the moons' orbits as a function of distance from the host planet.

Section 1: Introduction

There are two kinds of moons that are found in the Solar system. One type is the regular satellites, which revolve around planets at relatively closer distances from the planet in co-planar and circular orbits. On the other hand, over 90 irregular moons have been discovered recently to orbit the Jovian planets (Nesvorny et al. 2007; Gladman et al. 1998, 2000, 2001b; Sheppard and Jewitt 2002, 2003; Holman et al. 2004; Kavelaars et al. 2004; Sheppard et al. 2003, 2005, 2006). Irregular satellites, unlike regular satellites, revolve around planets at large distances in orbits that are inclined and eccentric (Nesvorny et al. 2007). Irregular satellites of planets are of immense importance to our understanding of the Solar system and its constituents. The orbital and physical characteristics of the irregular satellites help us to explain evolutionary processes including planet formation and satellite formation (Vokrouhlicky et al. 2008).

The origin of irregular satellites has been debated and it is not yet known with certainty. There are several hypotheses as to the formation of these irregular satellites. The standard model for the origin of regular satellites claims that they are formed by accretion in circumplanetary disks (Nesvorny et al. 2007; Stevenson 2001; Canup & Ward 2002, 2006; Mosqueira & Estrada 2003). This model for the formation by accretion in circumplanetary disks, however, cannot be applied to the origin of irregular satellites for several reasons (Nesvorny et al. 2007). First, irregular satellites are at great distances from regular satellites, which prevents them from forming from the same circumplanetary disk as that of regular satellites (Nesvorny et al. 2007). Secondly, irregular satellites have high eccentricities which are too great such that they make it unlikely that the irregular satellites were formed simply from accretion (Nesvorny et al. 2007). Lastly,

most irregular satellites have retrograde orbits which implies that they move in orbit around planets in a direction opposite to the direction of rotation of the planet (Nesvorny et al. 2007). These retrograde orbits, once again, disallow the irregular satellites to be formed from the same disk as the regular satellites (Nesvorny et al. 2007).

Due to the failure of the above model to explain the formation of irregular satellites, another model has been suggested to explain such formation. It includes the capture by planets from heliocentric orbits (Nesvorny et al. 2007). Irregular satellites can be captured from heliocentric orbits (1) through the dissipation of their orbital energy via gas drag (Nesvorny et al. 2007; Pollack et al. 1979; Cuk & Burns 2004; Kortenkamp 2005), (2) through collisions between planetesimals (Nesvorny et al. 2007; Colombo & Franklin 1971) or (3) through a pull-down capture mechanism whereby the planet gradually grows which leads to capture of objects (Nesvorny et al. 2007; Heppenheimer & Porco 1977). All of these models have difficulties in adequately explaining the origin of irregular moons. Model 3 has the drawback that it does not take into account the effects of the circumplanetary disk which is present when the planets are growing (Nesvorny et al. 2007). In model 2, the orbital change required for a collision requires there to be a large collider, the size of which is greater than the threshold for a significant collision (Nesvorny et al. 2007). Finally, model 1 also has its problems in that it is unable to explain the origin of the more numerous retrograde satellites of Jupiter, whose orbits are much larger than the radii of the circumplanetary gas disk considered by Cuk & Burns (2004) (Nesvorny et al. 2007). Because of the varying characteristics of the circumplanetary disks of Uranus and Neptune (Pollack et al. 1991, 1996), together with their low gas-to-solid ratios, it is unclear whether model 1 can apply to the irregular satellites of Uranus and Neptune (Nesvorny et al. 2007). Therefore, for all these reasons, this model of capture by planets from heliocentric orbits fails to adequately explain the origin of the numerous irregular satellites observed in our Solar system.

Therefore, we propose an alternative model for the origin of irregular satellites. From observations that astronomers have made about planets in our Solar system as well as of exoplanets, we observe that some of their orbits are inclined and eccentric, as a result of the gravitational scattering between planets (Chatterjee et al. 2008). Our hypothesis is that irregular satellites were formed from the gravitational scattering of regular satellites, in a similar way. In this model, two or more regular satellites gravitationally interact with each other to exert kicks on each other. These kicks can be so large, depending on the masses of the moons in the system, as well as their separations and distances from the host planet, that they cause the regular satellite to be pushed to orbits of high eccentricities and inclinations, farther away from the planet. These kicks can also result in ejection of the regular moon from orbit around the planet, if its resulting velocity (due to its own orbital velocity around the planet as well as the kick velocity) is greater than the escape velocity from the planet. In this case, the regular satellite may get kicked beyond the region of the Hill Sphere of the planet (the region where a satellite can exist in a stable orbit around a planet) and becomes an asteroid, comet or a Kuiper belt object. These kicks can also result in retrograde orbits.

In this paper, we analyse the range of possible regions, given certain system parameters, whereby the satellite-satellite-planet system becomes unstable, for given planets and their given satellites, by keeping some parameters fixed, while varying others. We obtain instability phase spaces for

Jupiter and its two moons, Ganymede and Callisto; Saturn and its two moons, Titan and Rhea; and Uranus and its two moons, Titania and Oberon. First, we keep the masses of the moons fixed and obtain the instability phase space by varying the distances of the moons from their host planet. Next, we keep the distances of the moons from their host planet fixed, while varying their masses. Using a given condition for instability (see Section 2), we obtain the instability phase spaces in Section 2. We then go further to analyze the sizes of the kicks that can be obtained in such unstable regions. For the three systems mentioned above, we determine the sizes of the eccentricities and inclinations that can be obtained from the kick from a given moon in the system. We plot the eccentricities and inclinations that result for a moon affected by these kicks, as the distance of the moon from its host planet varies. We also analyze the region from a host planet, whereby the kick can be so large that it causes the moon being kicked to be ejected from the Hill Sphere of the planet. We plot the ejection regions for the three moon-moon-planet systems under consideration in this paper, in Section 2.

Section 2: Models for the origin of irregular moons

Our method of testing our hypothesis makes use of several models to find the instability regions around the Solar system's three biggest planets of Jupiter, Saturn and Uranus, together with their two biggest moons. We then proceed to further find the regions within these unstable regions under which the possible outcomes of instability including eccentricity and inclination excitation and ejection could take place.

We begin by finding the instability regions for each system of planet and its two moons. For this, we give a brief summary of the necessary theoretical background that allows us to determine the instability phase space. Firstly, of immense importance is the Hill Radius of an object - the Hill Radius is the region around an object within which another object can exist in a stable orbit around it. For a planet orbiting the Sun, the Hill Radius is given by:

$$RHill(a) = \left(\frac{M_p}{3 * M_{sun}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} * a$$

Where M_p is the mass of the planet, M_{sun} is the mass of the Sun and a is the distance of the planet from the Sun.

For a system of two moons orbiting a planet, the Hill Radius is the region within which the two moons can exist in a stable orbit around the planet, without any perturbations between the moons or between moon and planet causing the system to be unstable. Using the above equation for the Hill Radius of a planet around the Sun, and considering the two moon masses as a single mass existing at the center of mass of the two-moon system, we obtain the Hill Radius for the system of two moons around the planet as:

$$RHill(a1, a2) = \left[\frac{m1 + m2}{3 * M_p} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} * \left[\frac{a1 + a2}{2} \right]$$

Where a_1 is the distance of moon1 from the planet, a_2 is the distance of moon2 from the planet, m_1 is the mass of moon1, m_2 is the mass of moon2 and M_p is the mass of the host planet (Gladman, 1993).

The condition that we have for instability is:

$$r \leq 2\sqrt{3} * RHill(a1, a2)$$

Where $r = a_2 - a_1$, and a_1 is the distance of moon1 from the host planet and a_2 is the distance of moon2 from the host planet (Gladman, 1993).

Another factor affecting the stability of a system is the relative magnitude of the kick velocity to the orbital velocity of a given moon. The orbital velocity depends on two parameters, namely, the mass of the host planet and the distance of the moon from its host planet (its orbital radius). The kick velocity, on the other hand, depends on the mass of the moon exerting the kick as well as the separation between the two moons. The greater the kick velocity compared to the orbital velocity, the greater is the likelihood of instability.

Using the above condition for instability, we found the instability phase spaces for Jupiter and its two biggest moons, Ganymede and Callisto; Saturn and its two biggest moons, Titan and Rhea; and Uranus and its two biggest moons, Titania and Oberon. We plot the points as a grid, first varying the distances of the two moons from their host planet (from the radius of the planet to one-third of its Hill radius) and keeping their masses fixed at their actual values. We use the above condition to find the instability phase space for each planet, with the plotted points representing the unstable regions, while the surrounding space represents the stable region. Next, we vary the masses of the two moons (from 0.1 times the mass of the moon to about 100 times the mass of the moon) while keeping their distances from the host planet fixed at their actual values. We find another set of instability phase spaces for each planet and its system of two moons. The instability phase spaces are shown in figures 1-6.

Figure 1: Graph for the instability region for the system of Jupiter (mass $1.8986 \cdot 10^{27}$ kg) and its two biggest moons, Ganymede (mass $14.8 \cdot 10^{22}$ kg, separation from Jupiter 1,070,412 km) and Callisto (mass $10.8 \cdot 10^{22}$ kg, separation from Jupiter 1,882,709 km). Here we vary the distances of the two moons from their host planet and keep their masses fixed and use the condition of instability to find the instability phase space for the system.

Figure 2: Graph for the instability region for the system of Jupiter and its two biggest moons, Ganymede (separation from Jupiter 1,070,412 km) and Callisto (separation from Jupiter 1,882,709 km). Here we vary the masses of the two moons while keeping their distances from the host planet fixed, and use the condition of instability to find the instability phase space for the system.

Figure 3: Graph for the instability region for the system of Saturn (mass $5.6846 \cdot 10^{26}$ kg) and its two biggest moons, Titan (mass $1,350 \cdot 10^{20}$ kg, separation from Saturn 1,222,000 km) and Rhea (mass $23 \cdot 10^{20}$ kg, separation from Saturn 1,222,000 km). Here we vary the distances of the two moons from their host planet and keep their masses fixed and use the condition of instability to find the instability phase space for the system.

Figure 4: Graph for the instability region for the system of Saturn and its two biggest moons, Titan (separation from Saturn 1,222,000 km) and Rhea (separation from Saturn 527,000 km). Here we vary the masses of the two moons while keeping their distances from the host planet fixed, and use the condition of instability to find the instability phase space for the system.

The instability phase spaces for the cases that the masses of the moons are kept fixed while varying the distances from the host planet, all have a similar trend. These graphs show that for small distances from the host planet, the separation between the moons has to be almost zero (negligible) i.e. the two moons lie at about equal distances from the host planet, in order for the gravitational kick to have any effect on the stability of the system. However, for large distances from the planet, regions where the two moons are close to each other result in instability. As the moons go farther from the host planet, the separation between the moons that allows for the kick to result in instability increases. This can be attributed to the effect of gravitational attraction from the host planet, which becomes negligible as the satellites go farther beyond reach of the planet. Thus the kick can have a greater effect on the moon-moon system, as it is less gravitationally bound to the planet. At smaller distances to the planet, however, greater separations between the moons do not allow for instability, as the system is more gravitationally bound, which prevents the distortion of the orbits to high eccentricities and inclinations or even ejection of the moon from the system.

The instability phase spaces for the case that the distances of the moons from the planets are kept fixed while varying the masses of the moons, also show a common trend. They show that for low masses of the satellites, the system is stable, whereas for higher masses, the kicks result in instability. This can, once again, be attributed to the same reason that at a fixed distance from the host planet, only when the masses of the moons are large enough that they are able to overcome the gravitational attraction of the planet, then the size of the kick is enough to cause instability in the system. We see that this is a common trend for the case of Jupiter, Saturn and Uranus, each with their two biggest moons.

In terms of the relative magnitude of the kick velocity compared to the orbital velocity, the orbital velocity decreases as the distance of the moon from the planet increases, while the kick velocity decreases as the separation between the moons decreases. This can explain why at greater distances from the planet, a larger separation between the moons allows the orbital velocity to be small enough to allow for the kick velocity to have more effect, and cause instability.

On the other hand, at a fixed distance from the planet, the orbital velocity remains constant, whereas the kick velocity depends on the masses of the two moons. The greater the moon masses, the greater is the kick velocity, and hence the graphs show that at larger masses of the moons, the kick velocity is large enough to overcome the fixed orbital velocity at a given distance from the planet.

We then go further to study the possible outcomes that can result from these regions of instability. We determine the possible eccentricities and inclinations and the regions within these unstable regions where ejection could possibly occur. First, we find the regions where the kick from gravitational scattering is large enough that it could result in ejection of the moon from an orbit around the planet. The condition for ejection to occur is:

$$V_{\text{orbital}} + V_{\text{kick}} \geq V_{\text{escape}}$$

Where

$$V_{\text{orbital}} = \sqrt{G * \frac{M_p}{r}}$$

$$V_{\text{kick}} = \sqrt{2 * G * \frac{m_2}{r_2}}$$

$$V_{\text{escape}} = \sqrt{2 * G * \frac{M_p}{r}}$$

Where V_{orbital} is the orbital velocity of the moon around the host planet, V_{kick} is the maximum kick velocity from the specified moon within the host planet's Hill Sphere and V_{escape} is the escape velocity required for the moon to escape from the planet's orbit. M_p is the mass of the host planet, m_2 is the mass of the moon that is exerting the kick on any moon at a distance of r from the host planet, and r_2 is the radius of moon2.

Based on this condition, the region in which the ejection takes place is shown in the following plots for each moon of each of the three planets. The moon being used for each graph is the moon that is exerting the kick on the other moon whose mass is not relevant in this ejection condition, and only its distance from the host planet is relevant. The plots are shown in figures 7-12.

Figure 7: Graph showing the region where ejection occurs for a moon in orbit around Jupiter, when it is exerted by a kick from Jupiter's moon, Callisto. The region where the sum of the orbital velocity and kick velocity is greater than the escape velocity from Jupiter is the region where ejection would occur. The range of distances chosen for this graph is the 69,911 km (radius of Jupiter) till 17,717,209.8 km (one-third the Hill Radius of Jupiter).

Figure 8: Graph showing the region where ejection occurs for a moon in orbit around Jupiter, when it is exerted by a kick from Jupiter's moon, Ganymede. The region where the sum of the orbital velocity and kick velocity is greater than the escape velocity from Jupiter is the region where ejection would occur. The range of distances chosen for this graph is the 69,911 km (radius of Jupiter) till 17,717,209.8 km (one-third the Hill Radius of Jupiter).

Figure 9: Graph showing the region where ejection occurs for a moon in orbit around Saturn, when it is exerted by a kick from Saturn's moon, Titan. The region where the sum of the orbital velocity and kick velocity is greater than the escape velocity from Saturn is the region where ejection would occur. The range of distances chosen for this graph is the 60,268 km (radius of Saturn) till 21,823,021.66 km (one-third the Hill Radius of Saturn).

Figure 10: Graph showing the region where ejection occurs for a moon in orbit around Saturn, when it is exerted by a kick from Saturn's moon, Rhea. The region where the sum of the orbital velocity and kick velocity is greater than the escape velocity from Saturn is the region where ejection would occur. The range of distances chosen for this graph is the 60,268 km (radius of Saturn) till 21,823,021.66 km (one-third the Hill Radius of Saturn).

Figure 11: Graph showing the region where ejection occurs for a moon in orbit around Uranus, when it is exerted by a kick from Uranus's moon, Titania. The region where the sum of the orbital velocity and kick velocity is greater than the escape velocity from Uranus is the region where ejection would occur. The range of distances chosen for this graph is 25,559 km (radius of Uranus) till 21,452,164.97 km (one-third the Hill Radius of Uranus).

Figure 12: Graph showing the region where ejection occurs for a moon in orbit around Uranus, when it is exerted by a kick from Uranus's moon, Oberon. The region where the sum of the orbital velocity and kick velocity is greater than the escape velocity from Uranus is the region where ejection would occur. The range of distances chosen for this graph is 25,559 km (radius of Uranus) till 21,452,164.97 km (one-third the Hill Radius of Uranus).

From the ejection regions for the moons of each planet that is exerted a kick from a given moon, we observe for all graphs, that the region where the curve of orbital velocity and kick velocity combined lies above the curve of the escape velocity of the planet is the region where ejection could occur. The graphs show that these regions occur where the moon is at least a certain distance away from the planet (where the two curves intersect) and all distances above that distance result in ejection. This is because at higher distances from the planet, the velocity required to escape from orbit around the planet becomes smaller, and it is easier for the kick velocity to overcome this escape velocity. The graphs for all the three planets show the same trends.

Next, we determine the possible inclinations and eccentricities that could result within these regions of instability. The inclination is given by the inverse of the tangent of the velocity perpendicular to the plane of orbit divided by the velocity in the plane of orbit. Figure 13 shows an illustration of the velocities that determine the resulting inclination produced:

Figure 13: Diagram showing the inclination produced from the kick velocity in the direction perpendicular to the plane of orbit, and the orbital velocity in the plane of orbit.

$$V_{\text{orbital}} = \sqrt{G * \frac{M_p}{r}}$$

$$V_{\text{kick}} = \sqrt{2 * G * \frac{m_2}{r_2}}$$

$$i = \text{inclination} = \arctan\left(\frac{V_{\text{kick}}}{V_{\text{orbital}}}\right)$$

Eccentricity, on the other hand, depends on the components of the kick velocities in the plane of orbit of the moon around the host planet. Figure 14 shows a diagram illustrating the velocities that determine the eccentricity of the moon:

Figure 14: Diagram showing the different components of the kick velocity that is exerted on a regular moon from another moon in the system and that the eccentricity is affected by the x- and y-components of the kick velocity.

While inclination only depended on the z-component of the kick velocity, $V_{z_{kick}}$, eccentricity on the other hand depends on the y- and x-component of the kick velocity. Therefore, we conclude that the eccentricity equals twice the inclination:

$$e = 2*i$$

Using these conditions, we plotted the graphs for the eccentricities and inclinations of the two biggest moons of Jupiter, Saturn and Uranus versus distance from the host planet and obtained in figures 15 – 17.

Figure 15: Graph showing the maximum eccentricities and inclinations that could occur in the unstable region for the moons of Jupiter, Ganymede and Callisto, as their distances from Jupiter vary. The circle shapes represent the actual eccentricity (0.0013) and inclination (0.0035 rad) of Ganymede while the triangle symbols represent the actual eccentricity (0.0074) and inclination (0.0034 rad) of Callisto, each at their original distances from Jupiter.

Figure 16: Graph showing the maximum eccentricities and inclinations that could occur in the unstable region for the moons of Saturn, Titan and Rhea, as their distances from Saturn vary. The circle shapes represent the actual eccentricity (0.0288) and inclination (0.006 rad) of Titan and the triangle symbols represent the actual eccentricity (0.00126) and inclination (0.006 rad) of Rhea, each at their original distances from Saturn.

Figure 17: Graph showing the maximum eccentricities and inclinations that could occur in the unstable region for the moons, Titania and Oberon, as their distances from Uranus vary. The circle shapes represent the actual eccentricity (0.0011) and inclination (0.006 rad) of Titania and the triangle symbols represent the actual eccentricity (0.0014) and inclination (0.001 rad) of Oberon, each at their original distances from Uranus.

From the graphs obtained for the maximum eccentricities and inclinations of the moons, we can see a trend of increasing (maximum) eccentricity and inclination as the distance of the moon from the host planet increases. For eccentricities greater than 1, the satellite becomes unbound and gets ejected out of the Hill Sphere of the planet. From the actual eccentricities and inclinations of the moons at their respective original distances from their planet, we can see that they each lie below the curves of maximum eccentricities and inclinations.

Discussion and Conclusion

From the analysis carried out in this project, we obtained the instability phase spaces for the two biggest moons of Jupiter, Saturn and Uranus. From our results, we can conclude that moons comparable to the size of the moons in our Solar system, could have unstable states (non-negligible unstable phase spaces). We also found the sizes of the kicks that could occur for given systems, with given parameters, allowing us to conclude that other systems of moon-moon-planet with similar parameters could also be unstable with such magnitude of kicks.

To analyze whether our hypothesis has succeeded or failed, we can compare the graphs we obtained for the maximum eccentricities and inclinations with the actual eccentricities and inclinations observed for the moons of the three planets at their actual locations from the planet. From such a comparison (with the actual data given in figures 15, 16 and 17), we can see that the actual values lie below the curve of maximum eccentricities and inclinations. This allows us to eradicate the possible failure of our hypothesis from the likelihood that the actual observed values lay above the maximum eccentricity and inclination curves. However, this does not give proof for the success of our theory. Further research and analyses may be required before a conclusion may be made as to the actual failure or success of our theory.

There are several implications of our results. The regions that show where ejection could occur causing the moons to become runaway moons could result in the moons becoming Kuiper belt objects or asteroids, outside of the orbit of its host planet. These runaway moons could also become seeds for planetesimals i.e. they could grow into planets by further accretion of materials in the region. These runaway moons, once they become planets, could undergo further gravitational scattering from other planets, and undergo the same effects as we have mentioned in our paper such as eccentricity and inclination excitation and ejection. These objects can then be scattered to become comets. The increases in eccentricity and inclination also have implications upon the system in which such effects are taking place. The very first implication of these effects is that they shed light onto our hypothesis that irregular moon were formed from the gravitational scattering of regular moons, as high eccentricities and inclinations are unlikely to have formed for moons formed in situ or by capture. Therefore, they give further support to our hypothesis. Other implications of high eccentricities could be that if the eccentricity is such that the moon is very close to the planet, then collisions can occur between the moon and its host planet. Additionally, moons in irregular orbits whose orbits cross each other (intersect each other), can cause those moons to collide with each other as well.

An analysis of the possible errors in our models can lead us to conclude that our models make use of the assumption that the moon-moon-planet system is unaffected by the gravitational effect of other satellites/objects in the vicinity of the system. In reality, the system would be much more complicated, with the size of the kick being influenced by several forces due to interactions with other objects in the nearby regions. Therefore, our model analyzes the ideal case of the system unaffected by other objects not being considered in the model. Additionally, a moon could experience several kicks from the same moon, one after the other, repetitively. We also did not consider this scenario. Furthermore, there could be secular evolution of the scattered satellites in that they can experience Kozai oscillations, which are periodic oscillations between the eccentricity and inclination of an irregular moon's orbit (Perets & Naoz 2009). Finally, further research can be carried out as to the long-term evolution of such scattered and ejected satellites.

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